

Two Probabilities in Quantum Mechanics, One Constraining the Other?

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Quantum mechanics is a probabilistic theory which differs from the usual probability of the classical world. In particular, many classical probabilistic scenarios are based on maximum entropy (minimum information) such as the toss of coin or die.

Here we consider two specific quantum scenarios which also contain classical looking probabilities, namely one dimensional reflection-refraction and 2-slit interference, in the sense of reflection-refraction probabilities in one case and one slit versus the other in the second. The point we try to make is that quantum mechanics in these two examples contains two sets of probabilities. There is the probability of the overtly noticeable events, reflection or refraction, or one slit versus the other, but a second probability for a constant momentum striking at different locations as governed by $\exp(ipx)$. In both cases, it is this second probability which governs the experimental results. In one case, reflection-refraction, the reflection and refraction probabilities actually follow from $\exp(ipx)$ continuity while in the second case there is an entanglement of probabilities in space from the two slits, even though each slit has a weight of 1 (i.e. equal probability as in classical physics-maximum entropy).

Thus, it is the probability of momentum strikes in x , $\exp(ipx)$, which is the constraining probability in quantum mechanics and must be considered along with a second, classical type of probability. When one compares classical mechanics to quantum mechanics, one usually considers only classical probabilistic features of both and ignores the idea of second probability in space from $\exp(ipx)$, we suggest, even though this follows from special relativity which is a classical theory.

Classical Probability

Classical probabilities are positive in the range $[0,1]$ such that the probabilities sum to 1. Two examples are the toss of a coin or die. A third example is the amount of time spent in each dx region by a bound classical particle. The point seems to be that there are two sets of variables, the probability and the state. For a coin, the states are heads up and down and the probabilities are .5 and .5 to maximize entropy (minimize information). Similar considerations hold for the die. In the case of a classically bound particle one has a probability proportional to $dt(x)$ and the state x with its constant interval dx .

Quantum Mechanical Probability

The situation in quantum mechanics is that one has at least two sets of probabilities even in the simplest probabilistic scenarios, not just the state and probability of classical physics. The first set of probabilities is due to the uncertainty of a p hit in x given by $\exp(ipx)$. The second set is due to classical type probabilities in a problem such as the slit through which a particle passes in a 2-slit experiment or whether a photon reflects or refracts.

In some cases, the position probability linked with the state p , i.e. $\exp(ipx)$ does not manifest itself as in the striking of a target. In such a case, one is only interested in the value of p . The

phase of $\exp(ipx)$ is of no importance. This is because once the interaction occurs, there is no tracking of x from $\exp(ipx)$ any longer. There are other cases, however, for which an interaction occurs and one must still track the x of $\exp(ipx)$. In such cases, two sets of probabilities may emerge with the $\exp(ipx)$ one being key and constraining the results. We consider two specific examples.

We suggest that the key or constraining probability $\exp(ipx)$ arises from the classical theory of special relativity. If one considers the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et + px$, it is degenerate for $t = t_0 + n \cdot \hbar/E$ and $x = x_0 + n \cdot \hbar/p$, where n is an integer. This suggests discrete resolution units in time and space which are consistent with the complex probabilities $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$, if one assumes $P_1(p_1x)P_1(p_2x) = P_1((p_1+p_2)x)$ and a similar consideration for $P_2(Et)$

One Dimensional Reflection-Refraction

In one dimensional reflection-refraction, the overt probabilities are that to reflect and to refract. If there were maximum entropy (minimum information), these would be .5 and .5 respectively, just as in a coin toss. The fact that they are not experimentally means that two momentum states ($-p$ for the reflected and $-p_2$ for the refracted) are treated differently. Thus, there must be some inherent second probability associated with momentum. Momentum is a well-known property which may be measured by striking the particle against a target.

This second probability is $\exp(ipx)$ which means that the probability to strike depends on x in a specific manner. This second probability is a constraint which holds in space even after an interaction at an n_1 - n_2 index of refraction interface. In other words, $\exp(ipx)$ is a probability based on momentum which holds before an interaction, while $\exp(-ipx)$ or $\exp(ip_2x)$ hold after, but still depend on x and p values. Physically, due to the uncertainty in x , even if the n_1 - n_2 junction is at $x=0$, the $\exp(ipx)$ forms mean that there is uncertainty in the p strikes at this junction point and one must consider a continuity of $\exp(ipx)$ s and first derivatives at this point as we have argued in a previous note, i.e.

$$A \exp(ipx) + B \exp(-ipx) = C \exp(ip_2x) \text{ at } x=0 \quad ((1a))$$

$$A p \exp(ipx) - p B \exp(-ipx) = C p_2 \exp(ip_2x) \text{ at } x=0 \quad ((1b))$$

The constraint imposed by the probabilities of the form $\exp(ipx)$ mean that different p values ($-p$ and p_2) are not on the same footing and the probability to reflect and refract are not .5. In fact, they are, for $A=1$, $B/B/c_1$ and $C/C/c_2$.

Two Slit Interference

Classically, a particle passes through one slit or the other and this does not change quantum mechanically. Classically, one slit is as good as the other and the probability to pass through one or the other is .5. This does not change quantum mechanically. We suggest, however, that the issue is that one must consider the second probability $\exp(ipx)$ and that the uncertainty in x is not just along a line of motion as usually considered. Experimentally, interference only occurs if the slits are separated by about one wavelength \hbar/p . This means that due to the uncertainty in p strikes in x , governed by $\exp(ipx)$, one cannot discern through which slit the

particle passes. Furthermore, after an interaction, the particle moves in space according to $\exp(ip \cdot r)$ and so unlike striking a target, one must still consider the effects of $\exp(ip \cdot r)$. In other words, there is a kind of entanglement in space of probability linked with $\exp(ip \cdot r)$. This entanglement is written as:

$$\text{Wavefunction} = \exp(ip \cdot r_1) + \exp(ip \cdot r_2) \quad ((2))$$

In ((2)), one acknowledges that the particle passes through either slit 1 or 2 with equal probability, but must conform to the constraints of $\exp(ipx)$ in space even after the interactions (at one slit or the other) occur. If one were only to consider a photon or particle hit at a particular x position on a screen L away, one might argue that there should be no interference. One might state that the particle/photon came from one slit or the other with equal probability and that all that matters is that there is a photon/particle strike at the particular screen x . In other words, phases from each slit would be considered irrelevant. This kind of scenario means that one draws a ray from one slit or the other to the point x on the screen. The problem is that this only considers p strike uncertainty in position along the ray when in fact it exists in all space around the two slits. If this were not that case, then one would not have the experimental result that interference only occurs if the slits are about \hbar/p apart. As a result, one must create a probability based on p and x for the whole region about the two slits and this is given by ((2)). One must, however, remember that now the probability scheme is in two dimensions x and y and not simply in x as one might guess from $\exp(ipx)$ along a ray. In other words, interference involves a kind of entanglement, we argue.

Quantum Bound States

In the case of quantum bound states, one has individual $\exp(ipx)$ s which interfere because one has uncertainty in time resolution of each of \hbar/E , where $E = p^2/2m$, so one cannot say that at such an instance t_1 the particle has p_1 and at t_2 , p_2 . One must again consider a kind of entangled state in space.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that quantum mechanical probability already differs from classical probability at the free particle level, because one has two sets of probabilities. The first is the usual overt classical probability, such as the probability to reflect or refract or to pass through one slit or the other in a 2-slit apparatus. The second is the special relativity driven uncertainty in momentum strikes of p with x , given by $\exp(ipx)$. In the case of a quantum particle striking a target, from the target point of view one is not interested in either the arrival phase of $\exp(ipx)$ or what happens in space to the particle afterwards. This, however, is not the case for one dimensional reflection-refraction or 2-slit interference. One must pay attention to the $\exp(ipx)$ type pattern after a collision. This means that for the n_1 - n_2 index of refraction situation of one dimensional reflection-refraction there is a constraint in space such that $\exp(ipx)$ s at the junction and their first derivatives are continuous. This means that one cannot assign probabilities of .5 and .5 for reflection and refraction. Rather the $\exp(ipx)$ probabilities govern these classical type

probabilities. In the case of a 2-slit apparatus, although it is true that a particle passes through one slit or the other with equal classical probability, the $\exp(ipx)$ pattern in space, now x-y space must be respected, i.e. the constraint of this probability holds. In the region around the two slits one has a kind of entangled state because there is not just uncertainty along the two rays, one from one slit and the other from the other. If this were the case, one would not have the experimental result that interference only occurs if the slits are about \hbar/p apart.